

INCREMENTAL PARALLEL CLASSIFIER FOR BIG DATA WITH CASE STUDY: NAÏVE BAYES USING MAPREDUCE PATTERNS

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ABSTRACT

Classification methods can be used to derive values from big data in the form of models, which then can be utilized to predict new cases. Several parallel classification methods for big data have been developed based on Hadoop MapReduce as well as for Spark system. As big data keeps on coming, the models must be updated from time to time to represent the old as well as the new data. The computations must be efficient and scalable for handling big data.

This research aims to enhance the existing parallel classifiers such that they will perform as incremental classifier handling batches of big data. The research results are presented as follows. First, the architecture and main concept of the enhancement is presented. Secondly, the proposed incremental parallel Naïve Bayes classifier (NBC) based on MapReduce that handles dataset with discrete attributes is discussed in detailed. Two series of experiment were performed on Hadoop clusters with 5 and 10 nodes. The results show that the incremental parallel NBC has acceptable accuracy, is efficient and scalable.

Keywords: big data classification method, incremental parallel classifier, MapReduce patterns

1. INTRODUCTION

Big data is high-volume, high-velocity, and/or high-variety information assets that demand cost-effective, innovative forms of information processing that enable enhanced insight and decision making [1]. It comes in structured, semi-structured and unstructured format. Processing big data requires new, innovative, and scalable technology to collect, host and analytically process the vast amount of data gathered in order to derive values. These values may relate to profit, medical or social benefits, or customer, employee, or personal satisfaction.

Classification methods can be used to derive values from big data in the form of models, which can be utilized to predict new cases. The required big data sometimes must be gathered from several sources and comes with different formats. This leads to complexity in preparing the needed data such that it can be fed into classification algorithms. The activities may involve advanced technologies, processes and algorithms. As big data along with other non-big data keeps on coming, the models must be “updated” from time to time to “represent”

the current data. To renew the model, batches of preprocessed big data can be produced periodically then fed into the selected classification algorithms. In this regard, incremental classifiers that work based on batches of preprocessed big data are needed.

Hadoop, which comes with MapReduce computational framework and works in distributed systems, offers many advantages for big data analysis. One of those is easy scaling of data processing over multiple computing nodes [2, 3, 4]. A MapReduce program takes input data in the form of key-value pairs. The Map and Reduce functions then manipulate those key-value pairs, and produce some other form of key-value pairs. MapReduce patterns, which are templates for solving a common and general data manipulation problem with MapReduce, have been developed [5]. Among those are summarization, filtering, data organization, join, meta and input-output patterns. MapReduce programmers can adopt these patterns to create MapReduce programs that are well structured and efficient. However, currently MapReduce framework only supports efficient computations that does not iteratively process big data as it accesses the big data from disks on each iteration.

Apache Spark with its RDD (Resilient Distributed Datasets), which can run on top of Hadoop's YARN resource manager, has been developed to address the MapReduce weakness [6,7]. Machine Learning algorithms that require iterative computations can be implemented on Spark. As in standalone implementation, the algorithms can then access the data from memory (stored as RDD objects), which is a lot faster than reading from disks. A Spark library of machine learning algorithms (MLlib), which has clustering (such as k-Means) and classification (Naïve Bayes, SVM and RandomForest) functions, have been developed and can be adopted.

Although incremental parallel classifiers that work based on batches of big data are needed, based on our literature study results (see Subsection 3.1 and 3.2), we have not found any technique based on Hadoop MapReduce and Spark that specifically address this problem. Therefore, this research objective is to develop or enhance the existing parallel classifiers that have been developed for Hadoop or Spark environment such that they will perform as incremental classifier handling batches of big data. The classifier must have approximately the same accuracy (compared to the existing classifier) and must be efficient and scallable. Having this objective, in this research:

(1) We reviewed groups of classification methods and identify which groups are suitable to be enhanced. (The group includes as Bayesian, decision tree, lazy learning, rule based and neural network [8].

(2) We studied research results related to those classification methods that have been enhanced or implemented for Hadoop and Spark, then analyzed the potencies of enhancement.

(3) Based on the above results, we designed the overall system architecture and the main concept of enhancement.

(4) From (2), we found that Naïve Bayes classifier (NBC) handling discrete attributes of dataset can be enhanced to handle batches of big data efficiently by adopting MapReduce summarization and meta patterns. It involves only one pass computation and read the training dataset once. Thus, we designed the detailed enhancement (as a case study) and conduct two series of experiments to evaluate the performance.

This paper presents our research results and is organized as follows: Literature review of basic concept (bagging, NBC, Hadoop and MapReduce patterns, Apache Spark, the evaluation of parallel classifiers and the main concept of enhancement, proposed parallel classifier architecture system,

detailed discussion of proposed incremental parallel NBC, two series of experiment for evaluating the NBC performance conducted on a Hadoop cluster, conclusion and further works.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Bagging: Ensemble Classifier Methods

Classification is a two-step process. First, a model is built from a training dataset. Secondly, the model is evaluated using test data set. If the model's accuracy is acceptable, the model is later used to classify new data. Depending on the "nature" of the dataset and the selected classification algorithms, the model accuracy is sometimes below the expectation.

Bagging is a method used in ensemble methods to improve classification accuracy. An ensemble for classification is a composite model, made up of a combination of classifiers. The individual classifiers vote, and a class label prediction is returned by the ensemble based on the collection of votes. Ensembles tend to be more accurate than their component classifiers [8].

Bagging works as follows (see Figure 1): D is a set of d tuples. For iteration i ($i = 1, 2, \dots, k$), a training set, D_i , of d tuples is sampled with replacement from the original set of tuples, D . (Because sampling with replacement is used, some of the original tuples of D may not be included in D_i , whereas others may occur more than once.) A classifier model, M_i , is learned for each training set, D_i . To classify an unknown tuple, X , each classifier, M_i , returns its class prediction, which counts as one vote. The bagged classifier, M^* , counts the votes and assigns the class with the most votes to X .

Figure 1: Illustration of ensemble method with bagging [8].

2.2. Naïve Bayes Classifier

Naïve Bayes classifier (NBC) is a classifier, where the features of the vectors (representing tuples) are assumed to be conditionally independent of each other [8]. Given a vector $\mathbf{X} = (x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n)$, using Bayes' theorem, the conditional probability of \mathbf{X} having a class value of C_k can be written as:

$$P(C_k|\mathbf{X}) = \frac{P(C_k)P(\mathbf{X}|C_k)}{P(\mathbf{X})} \quad (1)$$

Because the features of \mathbf{X} is assumed to be conditionally independent of each other, Eq. 1 can be rewritten as:

$$P(\mathbf{X}|C_k) = P(x_1|C_k)P(x_2|C_k) \dots P(x_n|C_k) \quad (2)$$

In Eq. 2, if x_i is discrete then $P(x_i|C_k)$ is simply the number of tuples of class C_k having the value x_i (for attribute A_i) divided by the number of class C_k . If x_i is continuous-valued then $P(x_i|C_k)$ is computed using Gaussian distribution, by first computing mean and standard deviation of the attributes. The highest value of $P(\mathbf{X}|C_k)$ is selected and C_k is the predicted class.

NBC model can be materialized as specific structure containing all of the pre-computed measures used in Eq. 2, which is used to predict the class of the new tuple. The measures include the Gaussian distribution for numerical attribute and count of each class values (for computing $P(C_k)$) and count of each attribute values for each class value (for computing $P(C_k|\mathbf{X})$).

2.3. Hadoop, HaLoop and MapReduce Patterns

Hadoop, a platform for storing and analyzing big data in distributed systems, comes with master-slave architecture [2,3]. It has components of Hadoop Distributed File System (HDFS) and MapReduce. Its storage and computational capabilities scale with the addition of slave nodes to a Hadoop cluster, and can reach volume sizes in the petabytes on clusters with thousands of hosts. A brief overview of HDFS and MapReduce is as follows.

HDFS: It is a distributed file system designed for large-scale distributed data processing under frameworks such as MapReduce and is optimized for high throughput. It automatically re-replicates data blocks on nodes (the default is 3 replications).

MapReduce: It is a data processing model that has the advantage of easy scaling of data processing over multiple computing nodes. Map and Reduce functions run in each slave node in parallel. A

MapReduce program processes data by manipulating key-value pairs in the general form:

map: $(k1, v1) \rightarrow \text{list}(k2, v2)$

reduce: $(k2, \text{list}(v2)) \rightarrow \text{list}(k3, v3)$.

Map reads (key, value) pairs, then based on the algorithm designed by developers, it generates one or more output pairs $\text{list}(k2, v2)$. Through a complex shuffle and sort phase, the output pairs are partitioned and then transferred to Reducer: Pairs with the same key are grouped together as $(k2, \text{list}(v2))$ and then each partition with unique value of $k2$ is sent to a Reducer. The Reduce function (with a specific algorithm assigned) generates the final output pairs $\text{list}(k3, v3)$ for each group (see Figure 2).

A client submits a MapReduce job to the master, which then assign and manage Map and Reduce job parts to slave nodes. Map reads and processes blocks of files stored locally in the slave node, sent list of key-value to Reduce via shuffle and sort, then Reduce may write its computation results to HDFS.

Figure 2: Map, shuffle and sort, and reduce phases.

If a job has iterative computation (calls its Map and Reduce functions many times until a certain condition is met), at each iteration, the process shown in Figure 2 is executed and the blocks containing the data being processed is read (again). It is known that reading data from disk, especially large sizes, cost I/O process that degrades the job performance. Therefore, any MapReduce job that has iterative computation (found in algorithms of data mining, web ranking, graph processing, model fitting, and so on), in which the whole data is read and processed, is not efficient.

To address that Hadoop disadvantage, HaLoop is currently developed (see <https://code.google.com/archive/p/haloop/>).

HaLoop not only extends MapReduce with programming support for iterative applications, but also improves their efficiency by making the task scheduler loop-aware and by adding various caching mechanisms. In short, HaLoop has the following features: (1) Provide caching options for loop-invariant data access, (2) let users reuse major building blocks from applications' Hadoop implementations, and (3) have similar intra-job fault-tolerance mechanisms to Hadoop. HaLoop is backward-compatible with Hadoop jobs. However, currently, HaLoop is only a prototype system and has not been released a production system.

MapReduce Design Pattern

MapReduce design pattern is a template for solving a common and general data manipulation problem with MapReduce. It is not specific to a domain such as text processing or graph analysis, but it is a general approach to solving a problem intended to build better software [5]. As MapReduce is a relatively new technology with a fast adoption rate and there are new developers joining the community every day, the design patterns also provide a common language for teams working together on MapReduce problems. There are several MapReduce design patterns that have been designed, such as summarization, filtering, data organization, join, input and output and meta patterns. Below is the excerpt of patterns that are adopted in our proposed technique, which are summarization and meta patterns.

Summarization Pattern

Data can be large and “vast”, with more data coming into the system every day. This pattern aims to produce a top-level, summarized view of the data such that ones can glean insights not available from looking at a localized set of records alone. Summarization analytics are all about grouping similar data together and then performing an operation such as calculating a statistic, building an index, or just simply counting. The summarization patterns include numerical summarizations, inverted index, and counting with counters. They are more straightforward applications of MapReduce than some of the other patterns because grouping data together by a key is the core function of the MapReduce paradigm: All of the keys are grouped together and collected in the reducers. If the value fields emitted by the mapper is the ones intended to

be grouped by the key, the grouping is all handled by the MapReduce framework for “free”.

Numerical Summarizations: The numerical summarizations pattern is a general pattern for calculating aggregate statistical values over the data. The intention of this pattern is to group records together by a key field and calculate a numerical aggregate per group to get a top-level view of the larger data set. The summarization function, θ , is executed over some list of values $(v_1, v_2, v_3, \dots, v_n)$ to find a value λ , i.e. $\lambda = \theta(v_1, v_2, v_3, \dots, v_n)$. Examples of θ are counting, minimum, maximum, average, median, and standard deviation. Numerical summarizations should be used when both of the following are true: The data is numerical or countable and can be grouped by specific fields. This pattern is generally used in word count, record count, finding min/max/count and average/median/standard deviation.

The numerical summarization generally has three components as follows:

- (a) The mapper outputs keys that consist of each field to group by, and values consisting of any pertinent numerical items.
- (b) The combiner can greatly reduce the number of intermediate key/value pairs to be sent across the network to the reducers for some numerical summarization functions. If the function θ is an associative and commutative operation, it can be used for this purpose.
- (c) The reducer receives a set of numerical values $(v_1, v_2, v_3, \dots, v_n)$ associated with a group-by key records to perform the function $\lambda = \theta(v_1, v_2, v_3, \dots, v_n)$. The value of λ is output with the given input key.

Meta Pattern

Many big data computing problems can not be solved using a single Map-Reduce job. Some jobs in a chain will run in parallel, some will have their output fed into other jobs, and so on. *Job chaining* pattern pieces together several patterns to solve complex and multistage problems. *Job merging* is an optimization for performing several analytics in the same MapReduce job.

Job chaining is one of the most complicated processes to handle because it's not a feature out of the box in most MapReduce frameworks [5]. Systems like Hadoop are designed for handling one MapReduce job very well, but handling a multistage job needs proper designs. Job chaining is suitable for a problem with a lot of job flows with complex chaining, where the first (previous) job generate lots of output data fed to the second (later) job. Job chaining can be implemented with the driver, JobControl, shell scripting, and so on. Job chaining

with the driver is the simplest method, where a master driver simply fires off multiple job-specific drivers. Here, the driver for each MapReduce job is run in the sequence as defined. The output path of the first job is the input path of the second. The first job must be checked for success before executing the second job.

2.4. Apache Spark

Spark is a general-purpose data processing engine, an API-powered toolkit which data scientists and application developers incorporate into their applications to rapidly query, analyze and transform data at scale [6, 7]. It is often used alongside Hadoop's data storage module, HDFS, but can also integrate equally well with other popular data storage subsystems such as HBase, Cassandra, MapR-DB, MongoDB and Amazon's S3. Spark's flexibility makes it well-suited to tackling a range of use cases, and it is capable of handling several petabytes of data at a time, distributed across a cluster of thousands of cooperating physical or virtual servers. Typical use cases include stream processing, data integration, interactive analytics and analyzing data using machine learning techniques. Spark's ability to store data in memory and rapidly run repeated queries makes it well-suited to training machine learning algorithms. It significantly reduces the time required to iterate through a set of possible solutions in order to find the most efficient algorithms.

Spark will normally run on an existing big data cluster. These clusters are often also used for Hadoop jobs, and Hadoop's YARN resource manager will generally be used to manage that Hadoop cluster (including Spark). When Spark runs on top of Hadoop, it benefits from Hadoop's cluster manager (YARN) and underlying storage (HDFS, HBase, etc.).

Figure 3: Spark architecture [7].

Spark employs master slave architecture with one centralized coordinator, which is driver and with

many workers (Figure 3). At a high level, every Spark application consists of a driver program that launches various parallel operations on a cluster. The driver program contains the application's main function and defines distributed datasets on the cluster, then applies operations to them. (The driver program can be the Spark shell, which takes operations from users.) Driver programs access Spark through a SparkContext object, which represents a connection to a computing cluster. Once a SparkContext object is created, it can be used to build *Resilient Distributed Datasets* (RDDs). Users can then run various operations accessing the RDDs. To run the operations, driver program typically manage a number of nodes called executors. For example, if the `count()` operation is run on a cluster aiming for counting file lines, different machines might count lines in different ranges of the file.

Resilient Distributed Datasets (RDDs)

The RDD is a concept at the heart of Spark. It is designed to support in-memory data storage, distributed across a cluster (as partitions stored in nodes) in a manner that is demonstrably both fault-tolerant and efficient. Fault-tolerance is achieved, in part, by tracking the lineage of transformations applied to coarse-grained sets of data. Efficiency is achieved through parallelization of processing across multiple nodes in the cluster, and minimization of data replication between those nodes. Having RDD, Spark supports efficient iterative computations, where each cycle needs to read large data, as the data is stored in parallel memory. Many machine learning or data mining algorithms, such as clustering, classification, association analysis involve iterative computations, thus are suitable to be enhanced for Spark environment.

A Spark library, namely Scalable Machine Learning on Spark (MLlib), has been available. It implements algorithms of classification, clustering, and so on. The classification algorithms are logistic regression, linear support vector machine (SVM), and multinomial and Bernoulli Naive Bayes, which are typically used for document classification.

3. PARALLEL CLASSIFIERS AND CONCEPT OF ENHANCEMENT

Based on its learning method, classifier can be grouped into **eager** and **lazy learner** or instance-based methods [8]. The former uses training records/tuples to construct a generalization model which can then be used classify new tuples/cases.

The later stores all of the training tuples in pattern space and wait until presented with a test tuple before performing generalization (usually, lazy learners require efficient indexing techniques).

Decision tree classifiers, Bayesian classifiers, classification by back propagation, support vector machines, and classification based on frequent patterns are all examples of eager learners. Nearest-neighbor classifiers and case-based reasoning classifiers are lazy learners.

If lazy learning is used to predict a class of a new case from big data, which can be petabytes in size, the computation will evaluate millions or even billions of records. This will be inefficient. Therefore, we conclude that lazy learners are not good candidates for classifying big data. Hence, we intend to find the classifier(s) that can be enhanced for classifying big data stream from the eager learner group based on Hadoop MapReduce as well as Spark.

3.1. Classification Methods Based on MapReduce

We found that few eager learner classifiers have been enhanced based on Hadoop MapReduce to handle big data. Aiming to enhance them into incremental classifier, below is our review of parallel decision tree classifiers, Bayesian classifiers, classification by back propagation, support vector machines, and classification based on frequent patterns:

(1) *Decision tree*: Decision tree induction is a top-down recursive tree induction algorithm, which uses an attribute selection measure to select the attribute tested for each non-leaf node in the tree. ID3, C4.5, and CART are examples of such algorithms using different attribute selection measures. In inducing a tree from the dataset, it adopts divide and conquer strategy in that the whole dataset is partitioned recursively. Early decision tree algorithms typically assume that the dataset are memory resident.

[9] proposes a parallel decision tree based on MapReduce via Sampling Splitting points with Estimation.

(2) *Naïve Bayes*: [10] and [11] have developed techniques to parallelize the NBC based on Hadoop MapReduce. From the results of experiment conducted in a Hadoop cluster with 4 machines (1 master and 3 slaves), [11] concludes that the executing time increases approximately linear with

the size of dataset and the size of data that can be processed is much larger than the standalone algorithms can handled.

(3) *Backpropagation*: Backpropagation is a neural network algorithm for classification that employs a method of gradient descent. It searches for a set of weights that can model the data so as to minimize the mean-squared distance between the network's class prediction and the actual class label of data tuples. Rules may be extracted from trained neural networks to help improve the interpretability of the learned network. In computing the weights of the network model, the whole dataset must be fed as many as the epoch (iteration).

[12] have developed parallel backpropagation neural network (BPNN) based on MapReduce. The training data are bootstrapped (partitioned randomly) into samples, each is then fed into BPNN running in every client machine. In the training phase, the ensemble techniques including bootstrapping and majority voting have been employed.

(4) *Support Vector Machine (SVM)*: A support vector machine is an algorithm for the classification of both linear and nonlinear data. It transforms the original data into a higher dimension, from where it can find a hyper plane for data separation (into two classes) using essential training tuples called support vectors. This binary classification can be adapted to handle multiclass classification by constructing an ensemble of binary classifiers. Error-correcting codes can be used to increase the accuracy of the ensemble. [13] proposes parallel SVM based on MapReduce, which involve iterative computation.

(5) *Associative classification and discriminant frequent pattern-based classification*: Frequent patterns reflect strong associations between attribute-value pairs (or items) in data and are used in classification based on frequent patterns. Approaches to this methodology include associative classification and discriminant frequent pattern-based classification. In associative classification, a classifier is built from association rules generated from frequent patterns. In discriminative frequent pattern-based classification, frequent patterns serve as combined features, which are considered in addition to single features when building a classification model. [14] proposes MapReduce-Based Parallel Frequent Pattern Growth (MR-PFP) algorithm, which mainly consists of six steps.

The objective of this research is to develop efficient incremental classification method, suitable for batches of big data. Table 1 (located at the end of this article) presents the summary of the mapper and reducer tasks and the job.

3.2. Classification Methods for Spark

Unlike the ones designed based on MapReduce, the related research results of classifications methods for Spark that we found are basically the application of MLLib functions (Naïve Bayes, Logistic Regression, SVM and Random Forest). The excerpts are as follows:

(1) Parallel Naïve Bayes (NB) and Logistic Regression (LR) algorithms are used to classify large scale of Arabic Text [15]. Large-scale Arabic text corpuses are collected, followed by performing the proper text preprocessing tasks (sequential text preprocessing and term weighting with TF-IDF in parallel). Parallelized NB and LR algorithms are used to classify the texts in the Apache Spark environment. The experiment results indicate that both NB and LR gives high accuracy (89% and 93%), but NB was faster.

(2) Experiment using Ensemble Support Vector Machine (SVM) was performed using big data with the size of 3T, namely, Splice-Site [16]. The experiment results prove that Spark provides a high feature throughput on cached data, and that models trained in Spark reaches as good accuracy as algorithms trained in any other framework.

(3) [17] proposes Incremental Parallel Random Forest (IPRF) algorithm for data streams in Spark environment. IPRF basically optimizes the data allocation by designing RDDs that are distributed on the worker (slave) nodes and task scheduling for dynamic parallel optimization (but, the method is not clearly discussed). The decision trees are built using IPRF on the dynamic independent feature variables stored as RDDs in the worker nodes. The experiments were conducted using Solar Power System which consists 1,88,835 instances. Unfortunately, the experiments results are not clearly discussed. One result that can be concluded is that the the larger the streaming data size, the larger the error rate.

Thus, from the Spark classifier literature study it is found that: Large as well as stream dataset are handled well by parallel Naïve Bayes, SVM and Random Forest. The algorithms also reach good accuracy.

3.3. The Main Concept of Enhancement

The parallel classification techniques based on MapReduce and for Spark discussed in Subsection 2.3.1 and 2.3.2 can be enhanced into incremental classifier to handle batches of big data. The following is the general idea:

3.3.1 Using Ensemble Methods

Basically, all of the parallel classification methods [11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16, 17] can be enhanced towards incremental ones using ensemble methods with bagging (see Figure 1). A batch of dataset:

(a) Can be split into one training data partition and test data. One additional model is constructed from the training data and added to the bag of models.

(b) Can be split into several training data partitions (similar to bootstrapping in [12]) and test data. Many models are constructed from these partitions and added to the bag of models.

On both approaches, the test data along with the old ones is then used to test the final bag of model. (It is also possible that the new test data only that is used to test the model. However, experiments are required to make sure that the model quality can be tested using that data only.)

Depending on the algorithms, the model can be a collection of statistic measures (for parallel Naïve Bayes), decision tree (for decision tree and RandomForest), NN model, SVM model or frequent pattern tree.

Issues and general idea of model constructions with MapReduce:

(a) The existing version of MapReduce does not support efficient iterative computation where each cycle reads the whole or part of dataset. Thus, the algorithms must be designed in such a way so that its number of iterations is as little as possible. Depending on the characteristic of the data input, this could be hard to achieve.

(b) Each Reduce function produces its own output (in this case, it can be “part of the model”). So, the algorithm design should include combining the Reduce outputs, if the job employed more that one reducer.

(c) Meta pattern can be adopted accordingly if the algorithm needs more that one pair of MapReduce functions.

(d) By design, Map function takes multiple files in an HDFS folder. The batches of data can simply be added into that folder.

Issues and general idea of model construction:

(a) Although RDD provides parallel in-memory dataset that can be read by Spark application many times, each task running in a worker will “see” and access its local RDD (the RDD objects stored in the node memory) only. Proper data structure and parallel algorithms must be designed to address this issue. If the task running on every worker is designed to compute “some part of the model”, there should be a mechanism to collect and combine all of the worker computation results properly.

(b) To address the above issue, one node can be designed to store one or more local RDD that represents ensemble methods’ data partition (which must be randomized). Then, the task is designed to create some part of the global model from those local RDDs. With this regard, each worker produces one (or more) local model (that later will be collected into bag of models).

(c) Spark provides mechanism of collecting RDDs from all workers into the master node. The global model collected (or combined) must be fit into a single machine memory.

(d) The Spark application may access HDFS, so the application can be designed to read multiple batches of data stored in an HDFS folder.

Materializing the general idea discussed above will need lots and tedious research activities.

ensemble methods, among of the methods discussed in Subsection 2.3.1 and 2.3.2, only one method can be enhanced. That is the parallel Naïve Bayes [11, 15] that handles dataset with discrete attributes only (which means, if there are numerical attributes, they must be transformed into discrete ones first). The model can be designed as the summarization (count) of the class and attribute values for each class value. When there is batch of data coming in, the new count is computed. The result is then used to update the previous (old) model (see Figure 5). Using MapReduce patterns, the method can be implemented efficiently as it involve a single pass computation only.

As the computation is simple, in this research this is the method that is designed (in detailed), implemented and evaluated through two series of experiments.

Figure 5: Steps of computing single model.

Figure 4: Core algorithm of computing bags of model on Spark.

3.3.2 Using Single Model

It is also possible to enhance parallel incremental classifiers that create a single model with non-degraded quality or accuracy. However, unlike with

4. PARALLEL INCREMENTAL CLASSIFIER SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

Preparing big data for classification, which may originated from many sources with various forms (structured, semi-structured or unstructured), involves complex processes. Those are data extraction and collection, combining or merging, selection, cleaning and transformation. To accomplish those tasks, few tools and complex computations may needed. Generating features from this data (for classification) would also involve complex computations.

Given these facts, we view that incremental parallel classifiers should handle batch of (preprocessed) data.

Our proposed general incremental classification system architecture that handle batches of big data is shown on Figure 6 and described as follows:

(1) Big data from external and internal sources are collected regularly. By applying functions for extraction, cleaning and possibly also merging and transformation, as well as loading, generally the

data is then stored in a data warehouse (along with other various data).

(2) Based on the classification objectives, batch of big data of interest is prepared, which involve selection, merging, and other kind of transformation (for preparing the features). The batch can be split, large part (70-90%) is for training and the rest is for testing the model. The testing dataset is accumulated in a certain location (directory) in the HDFS (some of the old datasets can be erased after largely accumulated, if necessary).

(3) The training data is used to compute the temporary (batch) model, which is then “merged” with the existing model. After it is merged, the temporary model is erased (so is the training dataset, if intended to save space).

(4) The final-merged-model can be tested using the testing dataset and then the measures resulted (confusion matrix, accuracy, precision, recall and f-measure) are saved.

(5) If by evaluating the measures, the model passes the defined minimum values, the model can be exported and used in other systems for classifying new cases.

On the architecture presented on Figure 6, the algorithm adopted in Proses 3 (to create and/or update the model) can be the one that produces a single as well as bags of model. It is expected that the size of the model is a lot smaller than the training as well as testing dataset such that it can be exported to non-big data systems and be used in operational systems as needed.

Process 3 and 4 can be implemented in Hadoop (with MapReduce) or Spark. As discussed in the previous section, however, Hadoop currently does not support efficient iterative computation. So, for iterative algorithms, Spark with its RDD is a better option. For non iterative algorithms, MapReduce patterns can be adopted to support efficient computation.

Figure 6: The proposed architecture of incremental classification system for batches of big data.

5. INCREMENTAL NBC BASED-ON MAPREDUCE

In our previous works [18, 19], we found that the most contributing factor that degrades the MapReduce job performance is its repetitive HDFS files reading (by the mapper). It costs lots of IO processes. On the other hand, parallel NBC that handles discrete attributes only has advantages (Subsection 3.3.2): The job is run only once and the computation for updating or merging the model is simple. Numerical attributes can also be transformed into discrete attributes using histogram analysis or other techniques. Based on these reasons, we adopt NBC as a case in materializing Process 3 and 4 of Figure 6 that creates single model.

NBC Model Structure

To support simple access and computations by Map and Reduce functions, the NBC model is designed to include:

- (1) The count of every class value with the structure: $\{class, value\} CLASS - count\}$.
- (2) The count of every unique pair attributes value for each class value with the structure: $\{atr_1, val_1,$

$atr_2, val_2, \dots, atr_n, val_n | class, value | DISCR - count\}$.
 ‘DISCR’ is included to indicate that the attributes are discrete (to distinguish with CONT for enhancement in the future).

Example of part of a model:

```
Play, No | CLASS - 7
Play, Yes | CLASS - 5
Outlook, sunny, Temperature, hot,
Humidity, high, Wind, weak | Play, no |
DISCR - 2
Outlook, overcast, Temperature, med,
Humidity, med, Wind, weak | Play, yes |
DISCR - 4
```

By using the above structures:

- (1) The Reduce functions (in the training and updating model process) can be designed to directly emit outputs with the structures.
- (2) The Map function (in the updating model process) can read each of the two structures as a record.

Module of Training and Updating the Model

This module consists of two jobs, which are job for producing a model from the batch of data and updating the old model using the newly created model. To “connect” these 2 jobs, Job Chaining pattern [5] is adopted. Two MapReduce jobs are designed (see Figure 7): The first performs model construction from the batch of training data, which outputs the temporary model. The second job merges the existing (old) model with the temporary model. The results of merging then replaces the old model.

As the designed NBC model contains counts of class and predictor attribute values, the numerical summarizations pattern discussed in Subsection 2.3. is adopted. In the training, the function of θ performs group counting over:

- (1) an attribute value of (v_i) , where v_i is class attribute and
- (2) list of values $(v_1, v_2, v_3, \dots, v_n)$, where v_i is predictor or class attribute.

During updating the model, the function of θ sums up the count of old and batch model for the same value of (v_i) and $(v_1, v_2, v_3, \dots, v_n)$.

The adoption of MapReduce pattern on the incremental NBC training (Figure 7) is as follows:

- (1) Job Chaining pattern is implemented with driver: *Job1* includes MapTrain1, CombineTrain1 and ReduceTrain1, and *Job2* has MapTrain2, CombineTrain2 and ReduceTrain2.
- (2) The summarization pattern with counting function is materialized in *Job1* (in MapTrain1, CombineTrain1, and ReduceTrain1) and *Job2* (in MapTrain2, CombineTrain2, and ReduceTrain2).

The overall NBC incremental training involves three stages of process, which are:

- (1) *Job1*: Read the incoming batch of training data and using the defined meta data, then compute the temporary NBC model. The model created (temp_batch_model) is then moved to the HDFS folder (/final_model) that store the existing model (namely, NBC_model).
- (2) *Job2*: Read newly created temporary and the old (existing) NBC model from /final_model folder and “merge” them into a new model. This job can only be executed after *Job1* is completed.
- (3) Replace the old model with the new one.

Those above processes will be executed whenever a batch of training data is fed into the algorithm. The detailed discussion of each job is as follows.

Figure 7: Incremental NBC training using two MapReduce jobs.

The tasks of Map, Combine and Reduce function of Job1 and Job2 are presented in Figure 7. As MapReduce functions work on the basis of pair key-value input-output, designing the proper structure (content) of key-value is important. The Map and Reduce tasks and the structures of key (k) and value (v) are described below.

Job1: Computing the batch model

MapTrain1 function: See Figure 7 for its tasks.

Input:

meta_data: Describes the training data attributes and classes with the following structure:

meta_data = class attribute + column number of class attribute + {attribute_name, type, index of column number of attribute} + count of attributes

Example:

```
@class :Play,4
@attribute :Outlook,0,DISCR;
Temperature,1,DISCR; Humidity,2,DISCR;
Wind,2,DISCR
@Count :5
```

(The attribute type is includes, because Map is designed to reject any tuple/record that has non-discrete attribute.)

training: The incoming batch training dataset with the following structure:

training = {attribute value} + class value

Example:

```
rain, cool, normal, strong, no
overcast, cool, normal, strong, yes
overcast, cool, normal, weak, yes
rain, mild, high, strong, no
sunny, hot, high, weak, no
```

Pair of *kl-vl*:

kl = offset of the record (line) being read

vl = record of training. Example: sunny, hot, high, weak, no

Output:

kl' = class|{attribute, value} + class

vl' = count of *kl'*

Example of pair of *kl'-vl'*:

```
|_class|Play, no - 5
|Outlook,sunny, Temperature, hot,
Humidity, high, Wind, weak| Play,
no - 1
```

CombineTrain1 function: See Figure 7 for its tasks.

Input: the same with the output of MapTrain1.

Output: *kl'* = *kl*, *vl'* = count of *kl'*

Example pair of *kl'-vl'*: sunny, hot, high, weak, no - 2

ReduceTrain1 function: See Figure 7 for its tasks.

Input:

kl' = class value|{attribute, value} + class value

list(*vl'*) = {count}

Example pair of *kl'*-list(*vl'*):

```
|_class|Play,no - [2,2,1]
|Outlook,sunny, Temperature, hot,
Humidity, high, Wind, weak| Play, no
- [1, 1, 3]
```

Output:

The output is written to a HDFS file. Here, only *kl''* is defined (*vl''* is set with null).

$k2''$ = class, class value, count | CLASS or
 |{attribute, value} + class + class value + count |
 DISCRETE

Example of pair $k2''-v2''$:

```
Play,No,5.0|CLASS - null
Outlook,sunny, Temperature, hot,
Humidity, high, Wind, weak| Play, no,
3| DISCR - null
```

Before Job2 is started, the file temp_batch_model is moved to the HDFS directory where NBC_model is stored.

Job2: Merging the batch and old models.

MapTrain2 function:

Input:

NBC_model and temp_batch_model have the same structure content, which is the same with $k2''$ of ReduceTrain1. As both files are located in one “logical” HDFS folder, the blocks created from the files spread across the cluster data nodes are treated as the “same” input by Map function. This function reads all of the local blocks sequentially.

Pair of $k1-v1$:

$k1$ = offset of the record (line) being read

$v1$ = line of NBC_model or temp_batch_model

Example of $v1$:

```
Play,No,5.0|CLASS
Outlook,sunny, Temperature, hot,
Humidity, high, Wind, weak| Play, no,
3| DISCR
```

Output:

$k1'$ = class + class value + “CLASS” or
 {attribute, value} + class + class value +
 “DISCR”

$v1'$ = count of $k1'$

Example: pair of $k1'-v1'$

```
Play,No| CLASS - 5
Outlook,sunny, Temperature, hot,
Humidity, high, Wind, weak| Play, no|
DISCR - 3
```

Steps of the function:

Read a string of line from the input split and store it in $v1$

Parse $v1$

If $v1$ contains strings of the class attribute and its value only:

$k1'$ = class + class value + “CLASS” and

$v1'$ = count of $k1'$

else // $v1$ contains predictor, class attributes

//and their count

$k1'$ = {attribute, value} + class + class value

+ “DISCR” and $v1'$ = count of $k1'$
 Emit($k1'$, $v1'$)

CombineTrain2 function:

Input: the same with the output of MapTrain2.

Output:

$k1' = k1$, $v1' = \text{count of } k1'$

Example pair of $k1'-v1'$:

```
Play,No| CLASS - 7
Outlook,sunny, Temperature, hot,
Humidity, high, Wind, weak| Play, no|
DISCR - 4
```

Steps of the function:

For every $k1'$

Sum $v1'$ from all pairs of $k1'-v1'$ having

the same value of $k1'$ and store it as new_v1'

Emit($k1'$, new_v1')

ReduceTrain2 function:

Input: Pair of $k1'$ -list($v1'$), where:

$k1'$ = class + class value + “CLASS” or
 {attribute, value} + class + class value +
 “DISCR”

list($v1'$) = {count of $k1'$ }

Example pair of $k1'$ -list($v1'$):

```
Play,No| CLASS - [7, 2, 4]
Outlook,sunny, Temperature, hot,
Humidity, high, Wind, weak| Play, no|
DISCR - [4, 6, 8]
```

Output: The output format is the same with the output format of ReduceTrain1 as they both write the same model to HDFS files. The output itself is written to a HDFS file. Here, only $k2''$ is defined ($v2''$ is set with null):

$k2''$ = class, class value, count | CLASS or
 {attribute, value} + class + class value + count |
 DISCR

Example of pair $k2''-v2''$:

```
Play,No,12|CLASS - null
Outlook,sunny, Temperature, hot,
Humidity, high, Wind, weak| Play,
no, 17| DISCR - null
```

Steps of the function:

For every $k1'$

Sum $v1'$ from all pairs of $k1'-v1'$ having
 the same value of $k1'$ and store it

as $count_v1'$

If $k1'$ contains strings of the class attribute
 and its value only:

Create $k2''$ = class, class value,

$count_v1'$ | CLASS

else

Create $k2''$ = {attribute, value} + class +

```
class value + count_v1 | DISCR
Emit(k2", null)
```

Module of Testing

The testing module consist only one MapReduce job (see Figure 8). The Map read the meta data, NBC model and testing dataset to compute confusion matrix, accuracy, precision, recall and F-measure. The Hadoop Map capable of reading multiple files from a certain HDFS directory. Hence, the testing dataset or files can be accumulated into an HDFS folder by the process that collects, preprocesses and splits the dataset.

The functions of MapTest and ReduceTest are described as follows.

Figure 8: Testing with one MapReduce job.

MapTest function:

The main task of this function is to predict the class value of a new case (read from test dataset). The files of meta_data and NBC_model are read by setup method to create objects of:

ClassContainer object that stores class values and ClassSplitConf that stores its location/index, name and type (must be discrete).

PredictorContainer object that stores all of predictor attributes and count, and AttrSplitConf that stores its location/index, name and type.

The test file is read line by line by map() method as k-v pair, the attribute values are used to predict the class value, while the actual class is also kept. The following is the description of k-v and k'-v'.

Input:

k = offset of the record (line) being read
v = record of test dataset. Example: sunny, hot, high, weak, no

Output:

k' = class attribute
v' = predicted class value + probability + actual class value

Example of pair of k'-v':

```
Play- predicted=Yes| prob=0.67.5|
actual=Yes
Play - predicted=Yes| prob=0.51.1|
actual=No
Play - predicted=No| prob=0.96.32|
actual=No
```

By receiving (k,v), the map function reads NBC_model and computes the every probability of v being in every class value (using Equation 2 as presented in Subsection 2.2). The map then selects the class value that has the highest probability and emit the predicted class, probability and the actual class as pair of k'-v' as shown above.

ReduceTest function:

The main task of this reducer is to compute measures, which are confusion matrix, accuracy, precision and recall, that are used to evaluate the performance of the NBC model (see Appendix A for discussion of these measures). Since all of the measures must be computed from all of the test instances (cases), to simplify the algorithm, a single reducer processes all of the k'-v' dispatched by all mappers (in other words, in the job configuration, number of Reducer is set to 1). This reducer implements the formulas depicted in Appendix A. The input and output are described below.

Input:

k' = class attribute
list(v') = {v'}

Example of pair of k' - list(v'):

```
Play {
predicted=Yes|pct=67.5%|actual=Yes,
predicted=Yes|pct=51.1%|actual=No,
predicted=No|pct=96.32%|actual=No,
}
```

Output:

The k'' and v'' are simply designed for grouping the output and easy writing to the output file. The k'' and v'' are described as follows:

k'' = class attribute + confusion matrix

v'' = accuracy + {class value, precision, recall} + F-measure

Example of k'' :

```
@Play
      |No |Yes| |
| No | 3 | 1 |
| Yes| 1 | 2 |
```

Example of v'' :

```
Accuracy = 0.71
Play = No, Precision = 0.67, Recall =
0.75, F-Measure = 0.7
Play = Yes, Precision = 0.75, Recall =
0.67, F-Measure = 0.7
```

Note: With this scheme, the job has the disadvantage in that all of v' must fit into a machine memory that run the Reduce task. Hence, the selected node must have sufficient memory.

6. EXPERIMENTS

Two series of experiments were performed with the following purposes:

Experiments-1: Proving that the proposed incremental parallel NBC compute and generate models correctly and have accuracy with the non-incremental NBC. Batches of dataset were created from three small to medium real datasets then fed to the classifier. The model that created incrementally using batches will be compared with the model built once using the whole dataset using the test output measures.

Experiments-2: Proving that the proposed incremental parallel NBC is scalable and executed efficiently in processing big data in the Hadoop cluster.

Experiments-1:

The experiments were performed on a single node, with CPU of Intel i7-3770 operating at 3.4 GHz, 16 Gb of memory, and running Hadoop 2.7.1. There are three datasets used, which are edible and non-edible fungi, nurses recruitment, and US homicide crime record by FBI, discussed as follows:

(a) Using **fungi** dataset:

This small dataset contains records of many kinds of fungi and its classification (edible or poisonous). It is obtained from <https://archive.ics.uci.edu/ml/datasets/Mushroom>. It contains descriptions of hypothetical samples corresponding to 23 species of gilled mushrooms in the Agaricus and Lepiota Family. Each species is identified as definitely edible, definitely poisonous, or of unknown edibility and not recommended. This latter class was combined with the poisonous one. The dataset size is 373.7 kb and contains 8,124 records. There are 23 discrete attributes, where 22 as predictors and 1 as class. The class values are edible (51.8%) and poisonous (48.2%). The predictor attributes are fungi's properties, such as cap (its shape, surface, color), bruises, odor, gill, stalk, veil, ring, spore, population and habitat.

Methods of experiments: First, the whole data is split 80% (as training) and 20% (as testing). After the model is created with the training, it is then tested using the test dataset. For experimenting with batches, we divide the whole dataset into 2 parts (as batches). Each part is further split into training dataset (80%) and testing (20%). Hence, we have 2 pairs of dataset to build and test the NBC model. Each pair is then fed into the NBC classifier to build and test the incremental model. When testing the model, the previous test dataset is also included, hence the test dataset is accumulated. The results is depicted on Table 2 (see at the end of the article).

From the results presented in Table 2, it is shown that:

(1) The model constructed using the full dataset is equal or the same with the model resulting from merging of Batch-1 and Batch -2 models in terms of its size and quality (accuracy, precision, recall, F-measure).

(2) The MapReduce job for merging the existing and newly created model takes longer time to execute compared to the training job.

(b) Using **nurses recruitment** dataset:

The data contains records of nurse candidate profiles and their rank of acceptance (very recommended, recommended, priority, specific priority and not recommended). It is obtained from <https://archive.ics.uci.edu/ml/datasets/Nursery>.

Nursery dataset was derived from a hierarchical decision model originally developed to rank applications for nursery schools. It was used during several years in 1980's when there was excessive

enrollment to these schools in Ljubljana, Slovenia, and the rejected applications frequently needed an objective explanation. The final decision depended on three sub problems: occupation of parents and child's nursery, family structure and financial standing, and social and health picture of the family. The dataset size is 1.1 Mb with 12,962 records. It has 9 discrete attributes, where 8 attributes are the predictors and 1 attribute is the class. Predictor attributes are parents, has_nurs, form, children, housing, finance, social, health. The class attribute: accepted, where the values are very_recom, recommend, priority, spec_prior, not_recom.

Methods of experiments: It is analogous to the previous experiment with fungi dataset. However, in these experiments, the whole dataset into 4 parts (as batches). The results are depicted on Table 3 (see at the end of the article).

From the results presented in Table 3, it is shown that:

- (1) The model constructed using the full dataset is equal or the same with the model resulting from merging of Batch -1, -2, -3 and -4 models in terms of its size and accuracy.
- (2) The MapReduce job for merging the existing and newly created model takes longer time to execute compared to the training job.

(c) Using **homicide** dataset:

The data contains records of homicide collected by FBI from 1980 to 2014, obtain from <https://www.kaggle.com/murderaccountability/homicide-reports> (downloaded on 29 April 2017). The size is 118.8 Mb with 638,654 records. Every record contains information of time, crime location, perpetrator and victim profile (such as gender, age, race, ethnicity), weapon, relationship between the perpetrator and victim, and count of perpetrator and victim. It has 24 attributes of numerical and discrete type. In this experiment, only the 10 discrete attributes which are relevant for predicting new cases are selected, which are:

Predictor attributes: crime_type, victim_sex, victim_race, victim_ethnic, perpetrator_sex, perpetrator_race, perpetrator_ethnic, relation, and weapon.

Class attribute: crime_solved, which has value of (solved or unsolved).

By selecting those 10 attributes, the size of the dataset becomes 56 Mb.

Methods of experiments: It is analogous to the previous experiment with fungi dataset. However, in these experiments, the whole dataset into 5 parts (as batches). The results are depicted on Table 4 (see at the end of the article).

From the results presented in Table 4, it is shown that:

- (1) The model number of records and their size may be increased from a batch to the next batch, but the final model is the same with the one constructed with the full dataset.
- (2) The model constructed from the full dataset is equal or the same with the model resulting from merging of Batch-1, -2, -3, -4 and -5 models in terms of its size and quality measure (accuracy, precision, recall and F-measure).
- (3) In processing small size of batches, the MapReduce job for merging the existing and newly created model takes longer time compared to the training job.

Experiments-2:

The aims of the experiments are to measure the execution time of training (*Job1*) and merging models (*Job2*) using batches of data with different number of discrete attributes on a Hadoop cluster. Four sets of synthetic data batch having 5, 10, 15 and 20 attributes were generated. Each set consists of 10 batches and each batch contains 50.000.000 records with size of 550 Mb (for 5 attributes), 1.1 Gb (10 attributes), 1.6 Gb (15 attributes) and 2 Gb (20 attributes). The values of the predictor and class attributes were randomly generated, each attribute has between 2 to 6 unique values. To measure the scalability, the Hadoop cluster was configured with a master node (name node) and single slave node, 5 slave nodes and 10 slave nodes, each node has CPU Intel i5-8500 with 6 cores running at 3 GHz and 8 Gb of memory. The master and slave nodes run Linux Ubuntu 18.04.1. and Hadoop version 2.7.1.

Methods of experiments: Every batch of data is fed to the parallel NBC running on a Hadoop cluster with single slave node, 5 nodes and 10 nodes. The execution time of *Job1* (training) and *Job2* (merging the models) were recorded separately. The results of every run are summarized and presented on Figure 9, Table 5, and Figure 10.

Figure 9: Execution time of model training and merging for 10 batches on 1, 5 and 10 nodes.

It can be observed on Figure 9 that:

(a) The execution times of model merging for 4 number of attributes are a lot smaller compared to the times of model training (see Table 5 for the percentages), and are relatively constant even though the size of batches varies. This is due to the fact the the models (being merged) are a lot smaller (10 to 15 Kb) than the batch size (0.5 to 2 Gb).

(b) Adding slave nodes to the Hadoop cluster improves the execution time. The larger the size of the batch (in the order of 550 Mb for 5 attributes, 1.1 Gb for 10 attributes, 1.6 Gb for 15 attributes and 2 Gb for 20 attributes), the wider the gap between time execution on a single node to on 5 and 10 nodes.

(c) The execution times of model training for processing batches are relatively constant. On the 5 and 10 slave nodes, by increasing the number of attribute and size of batch, the execution times are only slightly increased. But, there is fluctuation.

Table 5: Model merging/model training execution times.

# attributes	1-node	5-nodes	10-nodes
5	18%	20%	18%
10	9%	14%	9%
15	7%	9%	12%
20	5%	10%	10%

Figure 10: Average of execution times for batches with 5, 10, 15 and 20 attributes on 1, 5 and 10 nodes

On Figure 10, it is shown that:

(a) The average of *Job1* (model training) execution time on a single node increase sharply while the ones on 5 and 10 nodes only increase slightly over adding the attribute number.

(b) The average of *Job2* (models merging) execution time is relatively constant (with fluctuation) on the Hadoop cluster.

Thus, from these experiments, it can be concluded that:

(a) The MapReduce computation of *Job1* for producing NBC models from batches is efficient and scalable. Adding nodes in the Hadoop cluster reduces the execution time. The fluctuation of the execution times are caused by the shuffling and sorting process over the network.

(b) The MapReduce computation of *Job2* for merging the NBC models is also efficient and scalable. It runs a lot faster than *Job1* as the model sizes being merged are a lot smaller than the batch size.

(c) The proposed parallel incremental NBC (consisting of *Job1* and *Job2*) is efficient and scalable.

7. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORKS

The parallel classifiers for Hadoop and Spark that are grouped into eager learner can be further enhance to become incremental classifiers handling batches of preprocessed big data. All of the methods are potentially enhanced by adopting ensemble methods, which will be more efficient if implemented on Spark with its RDDs. Parallel Naïve Bayes classifier based on MapReduce that handles discrete attributes can be enhanced into an incremental classifier without implementing ensemble methods. Having the model be designed in the form of key-value pairs, it can be efficiently computed using MapReduce functions, by adopting MapReduce summarization and meta patterns, from batches of data. The old models can be merged with the newly created model (from the new batch) using MapReduce functions as well.

From the first experiment results, it is proven that the NBC single model can be computed incrementally based on the incoming batches of big data with accuracy that is approximately equal to the model built using the whole data at once. In testing the model, while the new case prediction can benefit from the mapper parallel efficient computation, the computation of measures are only handled by a single reducer. Computing confusion matrix, accuracy, precision, recall and f-measure needs to use the whole prediction results. In this research, all of these results are “collected” and processed by a single reducer only. Further research is needed to parallelize this computation.

From the second experiment results, it is shown that the proposed incremental NBC running on a Hadoop cluster is scalable and efficient. The time needed to merge the old model and the newly created model with a batch is a lot less than the model creation.

Further works: The incremental parallel classifier with ensemble methods need to be materialized such that preprocessed big data having continues as well as discrete attributes are handled efficiently. Big data may be in the format of texts, pictures, videos, graphs, encrypted, and so on. Developing parallel techniques to preprocess these kind of formats such that the results are ready to be classified is also required efficiently. Currently, we are researching methods for analyzing big graphs [20, 21, 22]. In the future we will develop the classifier for big graphs as well as encrypted big data.

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References

- [1]. David Loshin, *Big Data Analytics*, Morgan Kaufmann Publ., USA, 2013.
- [2]. A. Holmes, *Hadoop in Practice*, USA: Manning Publications Co., 2012.
- [3]. C. Lam, *Hadoop in Action*, USA: Manning Publ., 2010
- [4]. E. Sammer, *Hadoop Operations*, USA: O’Reilly Media, Inc., 2012.
- [5]. D. Miner and A. Shook, *MapReduce Design Patterns*, O’Reilly Media, Inc., Sebastopol, CA, 2013.
- [6]. J. A. Scott, *Getting Started with Apache Spark: Inception to Production*, MapR Technologies, Inc., USA, 2015.
- [7]. H. Karau, A. Konwinski, P. Wendell & M. Zaharia, *Learning Spark - Lightning-Fast Data Analysis*, O’Reilly Media, Inc., Sebastopol, CA-USA, 2015.
- [8]. J. Han, M. Kamber and J. Pei, 2012. *Data Mining Concepts and Techniques 3rd Ed.*, Morgan Kaufmann Pub., USA.

- [9]. Y. Cui, Y. Yang and S. Liao, PDSSE: A Scalable Parallel Decision Tree Algorithm Based on MapReduce, School of Computer Science and Technology, Tianjin University, Tianjin, China, 2015.
- [10]. P. Lucivnák, *Parallel Implementation of Dynamic Naive Bayesian Classifier*, Bachelor's Thesis, Department of Theoretical Computer Science, CTU, Prague, May 9, 2018.
- [11]. Q. He, F. Zhuang, J. Li, and Z. Shi, Parallel Implementation of Classification Algorithms Based on MapReduce, *RSKT 2010*, LNAI 6401, pp. 655–662, Springer-Verlag Berlin Heidelberg, 2010.
- [12]. Y. Liu, W. Jing and L. Xu, Parallelizing Backpropagation Neural Network Using MapReduce and Cascading Model, *Computational Intelligence and Neuroscience*, Vol. 2016, Hindawi Publishing Corp., 2016.
- [13]. Z. Sun and G. Fox, *Study on Parallel SVM Based on MapReduce*, Key Laboratory for Computer Network of Shandong Province, Shandong Computer Science Center, Jinan, Shandong, China.
- [14]. D. Xia, X. Lu, H. Li, W. Wang, Y. Li and Z. Zhang, A MapReduce-Based Parallel Frequent Pattern Growth Algorithm for Spatiotemporal Association Analysis of Mobile Trajectory Big Data, *Complexity*, Vol. 2018, Hindawi, 2018.
- [15]. B. Omar Alqarout, *Parallel Text Classification Applied to Large Scale Arabic Text*, Faculty of Information Technology, The Islamic University of Gaza, State of Palestine, October 2017.
- [16]. S. Lind, *Distributed Ensemble Learning With Apache Spark*, Thesis, Molecular Biotechnology Engineering, School of Engineering, Uppsala University, Sweden, 2016.
- [17]. A. A. Babu, J. Preethi, Incremental-Parallel Data Stream Classification in Apache Spark Environment, *Proc. of 1st International Conference on Applied Soft Computing Techniques*, April 2017.
- [18]. V. S. Moertini, G. W. Suarjana, L. Venica and G. Karya, Big Data Reduction Technique using Parallel Hierarchical Agglomerative Clustering, *IAENG International Journal of Computer Science*, Vol. 45, No. 1, 2018.
- [19]. V. S. Moertini and L. Venica, Parallel k-Means for Big Data: On Enhancing Its Cluster Metrics and Patterns, *Journal of Theoretical and Applied Information Technology*, Vol. 95, No. 8, 2017.
- [20]. Atastina, I., Sitohang, B., Saptawati, G.A.P., Moertini, V.S., A Review of Big Graph Mining Research, *Proc. of 2017 IOP Conference Series: Materials Science and Engineering*, Bandung, Indonesia, 2017.
- [21]. Atastina, I., Sitohang, B., Putri Saptawati, G.A., Moertini, V.S., An Implementation of Graph Mining to Find the Group Evolution in Communication Data Record, *Proc. of 2018 ACM International Conference Proceeding Series*, Singapore, 2018.
- [22]. Atastina, I., Sitohang, B., Putri Saptawati, G.A., Moertini, V.S., An Efficient Technique for Cluster Number Prediction in Graph Clustering using Nullity of Laplacian Matrix, *Journal of Theoretical and Applied Information Technology*, Vol. 97, No 7, 2019.

APPENDIX A

Metrics for Evaluating Classification Model Performance

This appendix presents the definition and measure formulas for assessing the classifier model, which are implemented in ReduceTest function (Figure 8) excerpted from [8] (Han, Kamber & Pei, 2012).

When a classification model is used to test a set of labeled tuples, it is defined that *P* is the number of positive tuples (tuples of the main class of interest) and *N* is the number of negative tuples (all other tuples). Other definition:

- a) True positives (*TP*): The positive tuples that were correctly labeled by the classifier.
- b) True negatives (*TN*): The negative tuples that were correctly labeled by the classifier.
- c) False positives (*FP*): The negative tuples that were incorrectly labeled as positive (e.g., tuples of class *buys_computer_no* for which the classifier predicted *buys_computer_yes*).

- d) False negatives (*FN*): The positive tuples that were mislabeled as negative.

For a class having two values (*yes* and *no*), a confusion matrix is described as follows:

		Predicted class		
		<i>yes</i>	<i>no</i>	Total
Actual class	<i>yes</i>	<i>TP</i>	<i>FN</i>	<i>P</i>
	<i>no</i>	<i>FP</i>	<i>TN</i>	<i>N</i>
	Total	<i>P'</i>	<i>N'</i>	<i>P + N</i>

For measuring the performance of classifier, four evaluation measures are defined as follows:

- a) *accuracy* (percentage of test set tuples that are correctly classified) = $(TP + TN) / (P + N)$
- b) *precision* (what percentage of tuples labeled as positive are actually such) = $TP / (TP + FP)$
- c) *recall* (what percentage of positive tuples are labeled as such) = TP / P
- d) *F-measure* (harmonic mean of precision and recall) = $(2 \times precision \times recall) / (precision + recall)$

Table 1: MapReduce tasks and job on few parallel classification methods.

Approach	Excerpt of the MapReduce Tasks	Job Running
Decision tree: Parallel Decision Tree via Sampling Splitting points with Estimation (PDT SSE) [9]	Numeric attributes is transformed into discrete attributes: sorted, discretize using equi-depth histograms. The discrete attributes are left as is. PDT SSE employs two MapReduce (MR) jobs: (1) MR ExpandNodes: Collect summary statistics (count of each class, count of each attribute value for each class) and store them in memory. The tree is constructed using these statistics. The jobs are repeated until up to a certain tree level. It then computes a set of data splits, each split should fit in the memory of every node. (2) MR InMemBuildNodes: Perform sub-tree induction in a node using the assigned data split (stored in memory) until the sub-tree is completely constructed. Then, the sub-tree is "added" to the global-tree.	Jobs run repeatedly. At each run of MR ExpandNodes (each level of tree construction), the dataset are read.
Parallel Naïve Bayes [11]	The proposed method does not handle numeric attributes. In constructing the model: The map function: Parses the label and the attribute value of each attribute. The <i>key</i> is designed as the label or the combination of the label, attribute name and attribute value, and the <i>value</i> of the <i>key</i> is set to 1. The <i>reduce</i> function: Count the frequency of each <i>key</i> .	The dataset is accessed once. The job run once.
Parallel Backpropagation NN [12]	Firstly, bootstrapping is employed to divide the dataset randomly such that each each partition fit in every node's memory, the partition is distributed to nodes. Secondly, MapReduce job is run repeatedly (up to max epochs defined) to process each partition and compute the NN weights. Multiple NN models (as many as MapReduce jobs) will be created.	The dataset is accessed once. Job runs multiple times in every node.

Approach	Excerpt of the MapReduce Tasks	Job Running
	In classifying a new case, majority voting is used. The ensemble classifier predicts a class for an instance using the majority of base classifiers.	
Parallel Support Vector Machine (SVM) [13]	The training dataset is divided into m partition. The parallel SVM is based on the cascade (hierarchical) SVM model. Firstly, each data partition is used to compute an SVM at the first level. Secondly, the support vectors of the former subSVM are used as the input of later subSVMs. The subSVMs are then combined into one final SVM in hierarchical fashion. A MapReduce job is run repeatedly to compute the SVM. In each run, the map train the SVM, then each reducer combines the support vectors of each two subSVM into one sample set.	Job runs multiple times in every node.
Associative/discriminant frequent pattern-based [14]	MapReduce-Based Parallel Frequent Pattern Growth (MR-PFP) algorithm mainly consists of the following six steps: (1) Integrate small files into sequence files (SF). (2) Equally divide the transaction data into several sub-transactions, then assign them to different slave nodes. (3) The 1st MapReduce job iteratively calculate the support count of each item, sort the results into I -list. Group I -list into G -list. Integrate G -list from nodes. (4) The 2 nd MapReduce job generate local frequent itemsets. (5) Aggregate those local itemsets obtained from each node into global frequent itemsets.	Job runs multiple times in every node.

Table 2: Experiment results with the fungi dataset.

Full/Stream	Train Size (kb)	Train Time (sec)	Model Merging Time (sec)	#Model Records	Model Size (kb)	Test Size (kb)	Test Time (sec)	Accuracy (%)	Precision Avg (%)	Recall Avg (%)	F-Measure Avg (%)
Full	299	13	-	191	7.3	74.8	11	95.8	96.1	95.8	96.2
Batch-1	149.5	11	-	191	7.3	37.4	11	93.3	94	93.3	93.9
Batch -2	149.5	12	17	191	7.3	74.8	13	95.7	96	95.6	96

Note: Precision, recall and F-measure are computed for each of the class values. This table presents the average.

Table 3. Experiment results with nurses recruitment dataset.

Full/Stream	Train Size (kb)	Train Time (sec)	Model Merging Time (sec)	#Model Records	Model Size (kb)	Test Size (kb)	Test Time (sec)	Accuracy (%)	Avg Precision (%)	Avg Recall (%)	Avg F-Measure (%)
Full	850	12	-	112	114.3	210	13	0.9	92.0	71	70
Batch-1	212	12	-	111	30.2	53	12	0.89	92.1	71	70
Batch-2	212	12	16	111	58.8	106	12	0.90	91.5	72	71
Batch-3	212	10	17	112	87.3	159	13	0.90	91.7	72	71
Batch-4	212	12	16	112	114.3	209	14	0.90	91.8	71	70

Note: Precision, recall and F-measure are computed for each of the class values. This table presents the average.

Table 4: Experiment results of homicide dataset with 10 discrete attributes.

Full/Stream	Train Size (Mb)	Train Time (sec)	Model Merge Time (sec)	#Model Records	Model Size (kb)	Test Size (Mb)	Test Time (sec)	Accuracy (%)	Avg Precision (%)	Avg Recall (%)	Avg F-Measure (%)
Full	45	22	-	135	7	11	16	99.9	99.9	99.9	99.9
Batch-1	9	15	-	127	6.5	2.2	13	99.9	99.9	99.9	99.9
Batch-2	9	13	16	132	6.8	4.4	14	99.9	99.9	99.9	99.9
Batch-3	9	15	15	134	7	6.6	15	99.9	99.9	99.9	99.9
Batch-4	9	14	15	134	7	8.8	16	99.9	99.9	99.9	99.9
Batch-5	9	15	16	135	7	11	17	99.9	99.9	99.9	99.9

Note: Precision, recall and F-measure are computed for each of the class values. This table presents the average.